

Research article

Updating the check list: new records of Psocodea (Insecta) from French Guiana

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Abstract: This paper reports six psocid species as new records to French Guiana: *Echmepteryx madagascariensis* (Kolbe, 1885), *Lepidopsocus marmoratus* (Banks, 1931), *Liposcelis bostrychophila* Badonnel, 1931, *Peritroctes trifasciatus* Badonnel, 1981, *Mesepipsocus brasiliensis* (New, 1972), *Archipsocus* cf. *minutillus* New, 1973. Two of them are also newly recorded for South America. A current checklist of psocid species in the department is provided, including the authors and localities where the species have been reported.

Keywords: Amazonia, biodiversity, equatorial, insects, rainforest

Introduction

The study of Psocodea in French Guiana has progressed slowly over about a century. *Thyrsothorus speciosus* Burmeister, 1839 was firstly reported by Enderlein (1919). Mockford (1965) recorded *Ectopsocus maindroni* Badonnel, 1931, and *Ectopsocus titschacki* Jentsch, 1938, from Cayenne. In 1973, Eertmoed described *Dolabellopsocus maculosus* Eertmoed, 1973, from Cayenne, while New described *Archipsocopsis nana* New, 1973, known only from French Guiana, and *Archipsocopsis virgata* New, 1973, also found in Brazil and Suriname. Mockford (1974) reported *Lachesilla sandersoni* Mockford, 1974, and other species from the region. Badonnel (1979) recorded *Ectopsocus thibaudi* Badonnel, 1979. Mockford (1981) mentioned *Psococerastis opulenta* (Navas, 1930) in Cayenne, and later (1993) included *Ectopsocus thibaudi* Badonnel, 1979, *Pseudocaecilius citricola* (Ashmead, 1879), and *Pseudocaecilius tahitiensis* (Karny, 1926) from French Guiana. García-Aldrete (2000) described *Lachesilla braticagua* García-Aldrete, 2000, *Lachesilla papillata* García-Aldrete, 2000, and expanded the known diversity of Psocodea in the region.

After a 23-year hiatus in Psocodea research in French Guiana, Georgiev (2023a, b) conducted the first detailed study of the species composition, primarily in the coastal area near the town of Remire. A total of nine species were reported as new for the department (*Echmepteryx pallida* Smithers, 1965, *Tapinella formosana* Enderlein, 1908, *T. maculata* Mockford & Gurney, 1956, *Maoripsocus africanus* (Ribaga, 1911), *Xanthocaecilius* sp., *Peripsocus ferrugineus* Thornton & Wong, 1968, *Ectopsocus ribagai* Enderlein, 1906, *Pseudocaecilius clunialis* Vaughan, Thornton & New, 1991, *Nepiomorpha* sp.), and one species new to science, *Tapinella montjoliensis* Georgiev, 2023, was described. Current study is a result the author's second visit to the region, reporting the discovery of six additional species to the check list, previously unrecorded in French Guiana, two of which were even new for South America.

Material and methods

Psocoptera were collected from French Guiana by beating the vegetation between 24.02–04.03.2025. The specimens were stored in 95% ethanol. The

Fig. 1. A – *M. brasilianus* (♀), lateral view, surroundings of Sinnamary River, B – *A. cf. minutillus* (♀), lateral view, Remire area, C – subgenital plate of the same specimen, D – *L. marmoratus* (♀), head with the specific pattern, Remire area, E – *P. trifasciatus* (♀), dorsal view, Remire area (scale bar for A, B, others not to scale).

photos (specimens in glycerin) were taken by a camera Canon PowerShot SX500IS through the eyepiece of a light microscope Optika. The material was deposited at the collection of the author. Systematic order follows Lienhard (2016).

Results and discussion

The study revealed six species as new records for French Guiana as follows.

Lepidopsocidae

Echmepteryx madagascariensis (Kolbe, 1885)

Material examined: French Guiana: 1 ♀, 25.02.2025, Remire Town, Sentier Vidal, 4°52'01.4"N

52°15'05.9"W, 26 m a.s.l., rainforest, dry leaves, beating the vegetation.

Remark: A species widely distributed at the tropical areas all over the world. First record for the Amazon region. Closest reports to French Guiana are Florida (USA), Chile and Argentina (Mockford, 1993, Lienhard, 2016), Brazil (Silva-Neto & Garcia Aldrete, 2020).

Lepidopsocus marmoratus (Banks, 1931)

Material examined: French Guiana: 1 ♀, 26.02.2025, Remire Town, estuary of Mahury River (Fig. 2A), 4°51'43.2"N 52°15'20.7"W, 7 m a.s.l., coastal scrubs, dry leaves, beating the vegetation (Fig. 1D).

Remark: New record for the New World. The species was previously known only from oceanic islands: Hawaii, Christmas Island, Indonesia, Fiji, Micronesia, and Polynesia (Lienhard, 2016).

Fig. 2. Habitat views of the Remire area near the estuary of Mahury River: A – coastal scrubs with coconut palms, locality of *L. marmoratus*, B – degraded plantations with scattered banana patches, locality of *A. cf. minutillus*.

Liposcelididae

Liposcelis bostrychophila Badonnel, 1931

Material examined: French Guiana: 1 ♀, 27.02.2025, parking area at the border with Brazil, near Oyapok River, 3°52'44.0"N 51°49'38.0"W, 55 m a.s.l., bushes near a road, from a pile of dry palm leaves, beating the vegetation.

Remark: Widely distributed, cosmopolitan species (Lienhard, 2016). New record for French Guiana.

Pachytroctidae

Peritroctes trifasciatus Badonnel, 1981

Material examined: French Guiana: 1 ♀, 26.02.2025, Remire Town, Lodges Balourou yard, 4°52'01.4"N 52°15'05.7"W, 20 m a.s.l., small rainforest patch, from dry banana (*Musa* sp.) leaves, beating the vegetation (Fig. 1E); 7 ♀♀, 27.02.2025, parking area at the border with Brazil, near Oyapok River, 3°52'44.0"N 51°49'38.0"W, 55 m a.s.l., bushes near a

road, from a pile of dry palm leaves, beating the vegetation.

Remark: New record for South America. The species was known only from Barbados and Senegal (Badonnel, 1981, 1983).

Epipsocidae

Mesepipsocus brasiliensis (New, 1972)

Material examined: 1 ♂, 25.02.2025, near Orapu River, Crique Margueritte, end of Rue Paganis, 4°37'04.5"N 52°19'38.5"W, 21 m a.s.l., rainforest edge near dirt road, dry leaves, beating the vegetation; 1 ♀, 03.03.2025, near Sinnamary River, below the dam wall, 5°03'59.6"N 53°03'01.2"W, 15 m a.s.l., bushes at the edge of rainforest near dirt road, dry leaves of *Heliconia* sp., beating the vegetation (Fig. 1A).

Remark: The species was known from Brazil and Peru (Lienhard, 2016). New record for French Guiana.

Archipsocidae

Archipsocus cf. *minutillus* New, 1973

Material examined: French Guiana: 1 ♀, 01.03.2025, Remire Town, hill near the estuary of Mahury River, 4°52'02.8"N 52°15'06.7"W, 27 m a.s.l., bushes with scattered banana patches, dry banana (*Musa* sp.) leaves (Fig. 2B), beating the vegetation, (Fig. 1B, C).

Remark: The specimen collected differs by all five species of *Archipsocus* reported for French Guiana by its short antennae. According to this fact, its size, the structure of subgenital plate, and colouration, it resembles *A. minutillus* New, 1973 (New, 1973) but differs by its wings which are not apically pointed. However, the wing morphology is not a key character for the species from the family Archipsocidae, and it could be considered for now as cf. *minutillus*.

The list of 36 species of psocids reported from French Guiana is far from complete. Although the psocid fauna of neighbouring Guyana and Suriname have not been studied either in detail, in Brazil (which is much larger), the known species exceed 400 (García Aldrete & Mockford, 2009, Silva-Neto & Garcia Aldrete, 2020). This indicates that many discoveries are still to be made, both in the rainforests of the

Amazon and in coastal and anthropogenic habitats along the Atlantic Ocean. A variety of collection methods, such as light and Malaise trapping, sieving, and sweep netting, should be applied in the future, and specific areas and sections of the jungle should be studied during different months of the year.

Updated checklist of Psocodea (Insecta) species from French Guiana, including authors and species localities, published:

Lepidopsocidae

1. *Proentomum personatum* Badonnel, 1949: French Guiana (Mockford, 1974); Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
2. *Echmepteryx falco* (Badonnel, 1949): French Guiana (Mockford, 1974); Remire-Montjoly, Wayki (Georgiev, 2023a)
3. *Echmepteryx madagascariensis* (Kolbe, 1885): present publication
4. *Echmepteryx pallida* Smithers, 1965: Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
5. *Lepidopsocus marmoratus* (Banks, 1931): present publication

Liposcelididae

6. *Liposcelis bostrychophila* Badonnel, 1931: present publication

Pachytroctidae

7. *Tapinella formosana* Enderlein, 1908: Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
8. *Tapinella maculata* Mockford & Gurney, 1956: Wayki (Georgiev, 2023a)
9. *Tapinella montjoliensis* Georgiev, 2023: Remire-Montjoly, Wayki (Georgiev, 2023b)
10. *Peritroctes trifasciatus* Badonnel, 1981: present publication

Epipsocidae

11. *Mesepipsocus brasiliensis* (New, 1972): present publication

Dolabellopsocidae

12. *Dolabellopsocus maculosus* Eertmoed 1973: Cayenne, type locality (Eertmoed, 1973)

Caeciliusidae

13. *Maoripsocus africanus* (Ribaga, 1911): Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
 14. *Stenocaecilius casarum* (Badonnel): French Guiana (Mockford, 1966)
 15. *Xanthocaecilius* sp.: Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)

Lachesillidae

16. *Lachesilla braticagua* García-Aldrete, 2000: Cayenne (García-Aldrete, 2000)
 17. *Lachesilla papillata* García Aldrete, 2000: Cayenne (García-Aldrete, 2000)
 18. *Lachesilla sandersoni* Mockford, 1974: French Guiana (García-Aldrete, 2000)

Ectopsocidae

19. *Ectopsocus maindroni* Badonnel, 1935: French Guiana (Mockford, 1965); Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
 20. *Ectopsocus ribagai* Enderlein, 1906: Remire-Montjoly, Wayki (Georgiev, 2023a)
 21. *Ectopsocus thibaudi* Badonnel, 1979: French Guiana (Mockford, 1993); Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
 22. *Ectopsocus titschacki* Jentsch, 1939: French Guiana (Mockford, 1965)

Peripsocidae

23. *Peripsocus ferrugineus* Thornton & Wong, 1968: Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
 24. *Peripsocus pauliani* Badonnel, 1949: French Guiana (Mockford, 1974); Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)

Archipsocidae

25. *Archipsocus cayennensis* New, 1973: Cayenne, type locality (New, 1973)
 26. *Archipsocus gibberophallus* New, 1973: Cayenne (New, 1973)
 27. *Archipsocus* cf. *minutillus* New, 1973: present publication
 28. *Archipsocopsis nana* New, 1973: Cayenne, type locality (New, 1973)

29. *Archipsocopsis virgata* New, 1973: Cayenne Botanical Garden (New, 1973)
 30. *Archipsocus vittatus* New, 1973: Cayenne, type locality (New, 1973)

Pseudocaeciliidae

31. *Pseudocaecilius citricola* (Ashmead, 1879): French Guiana (Mockford, 1993)
 32. *Pseudocaecilius clunialis* Vaughan, Thornton & New, 1991: Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)
 33. *Pseudocaecilius tahitiensis* (Karny, 1926): French Guiana (Mockford, 1993)

Elipsocidae

34. *Nepiomorpha* sp.: Remire-Montjoly (Georgiev, 2023a)

Psocidae

35. *Psococerastis opulenta* (Navas, 1930): Cayenne (Mockford, 1981)
 36. *Thyrsophorus speciosus* Burmeister, 1839: French Guiana (Enderlein, 1919)

Acknowledgements

I am grateful to Todor Mishev for the cooperation and help during the collecting trips in French Guiana.

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